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THE ROLE OF MEMES AND EMOJI IN ENHANCING CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract

The prevalent trend of using memes and emoji on social media has changed the landscape of communication across online platforms. Memes and emoji, despite being a popular online language, have received limited attention in the social media marketing literature. This study aims to investigate how memes and emoji can enhance customer engagement when incorporated into a brand's social media communications. In the first phase of the study, netnography was used to assess the frequency of emoji across three social media platforms: Facebook, Instagram, and X. A total of 2,800 social media posts and comments were analyzed to categorize the brands that use emoji more frequently. The results identified that the thumbs-up (👍), heart (❤️), and smile (😊) were the most commonly used emoji among brand categories such as fashion and apparel, food, makeup, entertainment, and transportation. Netnography was followed by a thorough content analysis to explore customer engagement, in the form of reactions, comments, and shares, with the brands' social media posts, which contained memes and emoji. In the second phase of the study, 20 in-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted to validate the findings from the netnography and content analysis. The results suggest that the social media audience favors 👍 and 😊 over the ❤️, as they are perceived to convey positivity and warmth. Furthermore, emoji and memes are more likely to be accepted by the youth, especially when the brands' communication resonates with their personality. Moreover, emoji can be used to express concern during complaint handling, resulting in a friendlier relationship with customers.

Keywords: *Meme Marketing, Emoji Marketing, Netnography, Customer Engagement*

1. Introduction

With the advancement in technology, numerous opportunities exist for brands to establish personal connections with their consumers. Social media enables brands to communicate with their consumers in a friendlier and casual manner. The social media platforms used by companies to encourage customer engagement include X, Instagram, Facebook, Pinterest, and LinkedIn. Additionally, Pakistan's investments in social media marketing grew to nearly \$64.43 million in 2025, underscoring the prevailing trend of leveraging social media. Moreover, social media users in Pakistan are expected to reach 244.2 million by 2029. This, coupled with the rise of smartphone usage is compelling brands to engage more creatively with digital audiences (Statista, 2024).

Computer-mediated communication provides immediate gratification but is still considered a "lean" medium due to its inability to portray the non-verbal signs that one might see during face-to-face communication. Non-verbal cues, including touch, eye contact, body language, and facial expressions, are essential for any message to be fully understood. The lack of these non-verbal cues can result in detachment from the sender (Janssen et al., 2014). Over the years, this problem has been addressed by several tactics such as the sender typically typed their message in capitalized letters to show anger, or through the use of multiple exclamation marks to show excitement, or demonstrating expressions through keyboard symbols (Harris & Paradise, 2007). These expression symbols, or emoticons, made up for the lack of non-verbal cues in digital communications (Negishi, 2014). The use of emoticons gave rise to emoji in recent years. Non-verbal cues can still be incorporated into computer-mediated communication through the use of memes and emoji. However, there is limited research about brands' use of memes and emoji to communicate with their audience.

Memes are "amateur media artifacts, extensively remixed and recirculated by different participants on social media networks" (Milner, 2013). Memes can exist in several forms, such as an image macro (image with text) or simply just an image, which is known as a reaction shot. These types of memes can be considered a form of non-verbal communication. They can serve the same purpose as facial expressions when talking to an individual (Grundlingh, 2018).

Social media platforms enable users to create, replicate, and distribute memes. Memes tend to tie users with their online communities (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Memes are generally formed with the combination of intertextuality, remix, and humor (Davis et al., 2016; Shifman, 2013). The global use of memes on the internet has constructed a new form of media lingua franca that creates a "common tongue allowing geographically dispersed participants to connect and share".

Similarly, emoji, which are pictorial renditions of facial expressions, animals, or objects, tend to amplify the meaning of the message and provide clarity between the sender and the receiver (Ganster et al., 2012; Fullwood et al., 2015). The use of emoji and emoticons has now become an extensive language that tends to carry more weight than words alone. Emoji cannot only demonstrate feelings and the sender's emotions (anger, sarcasm, happiness, sadness), but can also accurately convey what the sender did or ate that day.

The landscape of customer engagement has also changed over the years, due to the ever-changing nature of social media (Brodie et al., 2013). Customer engagement on social media is crucial for the success of companies across various industries, including retail (Godey et al., 2016), and sports (Aichner, 2019), among others. Online customer engagement plays a crucial role in creating and maintaining online brand communities which helps enhance branding (Hajli et al., 2017) and ultimately enables companies to gain a competitive edge (Kumar & Pansari, 2016).

Advancements in technology have opened up new possibilities for brand-consumer engagement on social media. Social media allows users to engage with posts through likes, comments, and shares, which are commonly used metrics to evaluate the level of customer engagement on social media (Mariani et al., 2016). However, social media users tend to avoid promotional messages on social media, and often do not engage with such branded content. Research suggests that customers are more likely to skip or scroll past brand advertisements (McDonald, 2018).

Therefore, there is a need to overcome this challenge by devising techniques that make it difficult for consumers to ignore them, such as incorporating user-generated content and utilizing emoji. A study by Sagin (2020) found that millennials typically ignore sponsored content but are easily influenced by user-generated content, such as memes. Memes are considered a highly engaging form of content that employs various affective strategies, such as humor or sarcasm, and are distributed across the internet in different formats, including GIFs, images, text, and video (Brubaker et al., 2018). Although memes have been recognized as the most successful and simplest mode of branded communications (Bury, 2016), there is still a lack of research in this area.

Due to the limited existing research and the growing trend of using memes and emoji in online marketing communications, this paper aims to highlight how brands can benefit from incorporating memes and emoji into their marketing strategies. Hence, the purpose of this study is twofold: first, to explore how Pakistani brands utilize memes and emoji in their online communications, and second, to examine how consumers respond to such marketing efforts. Addressing these questions will not only provide valuable insights to marketers and practitioners on how to communicate in a more modern way, but also to academics who can explore this topic more extensively.

1.1 Research Questions

On this premise, the present study intends to answer the following questions:

- What role can memes and emoji play in a Pakistani marketing environment?
- How do consumers view brands' use of emoji and memes in their online communications?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Internet Memes

Over the years, memes have evolved to be parallel with the web itself due to the fact that the internet has become a space that provides “an environment that fosters a participatory culture”. The Internet’s “ubiquitous presence and accessibility enable users to transform existing memes and create new ones very easily”. The fact that memes can circulate freely on the internet has altered internet culture, making it an interesting topic to investigate (Zanette et al., 2019).

Shifman (2013) has defined internet memes as “the propagation of content such as jokes, rumors, videos, or websites from one person to others via the Internet”. Internet memes are one of the most perfect examples of user-generated content. These are often created to add humor to rather serious and debatable topics. The use of memes in political campaigns is very common (Milner, 2013).

Scholars have described and defined memes in many different ways. The term “internet meme” differs from the term meme, and can be defined as “highly visual and emotive forms of online communication that include popular images paired with concise messages to convey meaning” (Bellar et al., 2013). They can also be defined as “multimodal artifacts remixed by numerous participants, using popular culture for public commentary (Milner, 2013). Knobel & Lankshear (2007) describe this term as “the sudden and widespread adoption of a specific concept or message presented in a written format, image, verbal expression, or other cultural element”.

Today, the internet world is filled with prosumers. The term “prosumers” was coined by Alvin Toffler in 1980, who described them as individuals who are both creators and consumers of online content. Prosumers have created a “participatory culture,” and the rapid spread and alteration of memes across the internet exemplify how this culture is transformed across different media, and why internet memes are considered a modern way of non-verbal communication (Katz & Shifman, 2017; Nissenbaum & Shifman, 2017).

2.1.1 Types of Memes

Internet memes come in various forms, including still pictures, pictures superimposed with text, GIFs (Graphic Interchange Format), and videos. They have become an important part of an individual’s online life. They bring a humorous side to some serious topics, such as politics or branding, or can be used for fun. Scholars suggest that the most common type of internet meme is an image macro, which is an image accompanied by text above or below it, that essentially lends a humorous meaning to the image (Dancygier & Vandelanotte, 2017).

2.1.2 Virality of Memes

Research suggests that virality is a simple two-step process, involving receiving and forwarding the message. The first step in the process of virality is likeability, which refers to how engaging the user finds that content. The second step of virality is shareability that refers to the extent to which the user considers that forwarding this message will be beneficial for others (Mills, 2012). Clicking the ‘like’ button on Facebook represents likeability towards the meme, and clicking ‘share’ represents the shareability aspect, which has a word-of-mouth effect. This

process puts that particular meme in competition with other memes. Memes only become successful if they become viral (Shifman, 2013).

Academia has recently begun to consider internet memes as a unique and distinguishing way of communicating a brand's marketing efforts, thereby claiming it to be an innovative marketing communication channel (Brubaker et al., 2018). However, with the rapid growth of social media, when marketers began using memes for their branding purposes, they were met with utter disgust and frustration by meme enthusiasts. The term used for this practice was "memejacking". Despite the controversy, memejacking, or better termed as "meme marketing", has progressed over the years.

As mentioned earlier, internet memes tend to spread quickly across the internet. They are further characterized as a type of content that is user-generated, involving the use of images, modifications, and humor. Thus, using memes in marketing communications can be beneficial for companies (Brubaker et al., 2018). The reason for this is that social media users typically share such content more often than they find interesting or can relate to on some level. Seeing memes online may incite users to share and even contribute their input, thereby creating memes themselves (Sela et al., 2019).

2.2 Emoji

When physically communicating with people, the sender conveys not only messages with words but also with their nonverbal cues, such as smiles, eye contact, and body language. Nonverbal cues convey emotions and intentions that complement the message for better understanding (Kaye et al., 2017). With the proliferation of social media, online communication often lacks the nonverbal cues that are typically used in face-to-face communication. The absence of nonverbal communication cues creates a barrier for the receiver to accurately interpret the intent and emotion behind the message. Due to the likelihood of misinterpretation in social media communication, consumers use subtle nonverbal cues, such as emoticons and emoji (Kaye et al., 2017). Consumers use emoji to express how they are feeling, providing an interactive component to digital communications (Derks et al., 2007). This discussion can be understood with the following examples:

Amna is having too much fun 😊 Amna is having too much fun 😡

Both of these texts are the same; however, emoji provide the reader with the genuine emotion and intent with which they are written, thus complementing the message for a better understanding. In the first sentence, the sender shows a feeling of happiness and joy, but in the second sentence, the sender portrays feelings of annoyance.

It is important to mention that emoji do not only portray human emotions (i.e. happiness, anger, surprise), but can also portray actions (such as a hug or thumbs up) and objects (such as a pencil, or chair) to give a complete understanding to the message (Luangrath et al., 2017).

2.2.1 *Emoji in Marketing Communications*

Visual representations have a greater capacity to enhance consumers' brand perceptions and brand recall compared to when information is presented in words only (Childers & Jass, 2002).

Some emoji convey emotions, while others are merely artifacts, yet they are of equal importance. They also play a role in shaping brand attitudes and perceptions, as they help consumers associate themselves with the brand. Not only this, but artefact emoji also enhance brand's message, making it clearer and straightforward for the audience. Therefore, it can be assumed that even if artefact emoji might not evoke the affective component, they can still clarify the message to a great extent (Riordan, 2017).

Recent work has focused on consumer motives for using emoji as a means of expression in social media messages. On the receiver side, research has examined neural responses to visual textual paralanguage, demonstrating that our brains react to a face-based emoticon in the same way as they do with face-to-face engagement (Churches et al., 2014). Emoji have been found to have the potential to reduce misinterpretations, convey emotion, and clarify intention (Kaye et al., 2017; Riordan, 2017). However, Willoughby and Liu (2018) find that messages with emoji can be perceived as less credible and elicit lower levels of elaboration than those without emoji.

Research suggests that emoji moderate the effects of customer engagement on social media, thereby increasing consumer brand attachment (Arya et al., 2018). On a practical level, the use of emoji is not confined to consumer interactions alone, instead, it is becoming a key strategy for effective brand communication. Prominent brands, including Chevron, Sony, Burger King, Taco Bell, and Coca-Cola, are incorporating emoji into their marketing communications. In fact, the trend of tweets containing both an emoji and a brand name has been increasing since 2015 (Agnew, 2017).

2.2.2 Communication through Speech Acts

In ancient times, cavemen used pictograms and visual representations to communicate. They easily conveyed their beliefs, thoughts and feelings with the use of images. This idea corresponds to the development and use of emoji in today's communication systems, which has become possible due to digital programming technology. Examining its antecedents, it is believed that emoji tend to convey emotions more effectively and provide a deeper understanding of the message, compared to when communication is limited to alphabetic characters (Azuma, 2012). Therefore, it is pertinent to examine the role of emoji in digital communications.

Similarly, memes can be characterized as speech acts; however, some memes are easier to interpret and used more frequently than others (Milner, 2013). A common type of meme, known as an image macro may become so popular on social media that the users often name such a meme. Some famous examples of such memes include, Advice Animals, Success Kid and Scumbag Steve. Such image macros and reactions can be classified as speech acts, as they convey the sender's intent without requiring them to say anything at all (Grundlingh, 2018).

People tend to share memes on social media to build stronger connections with the community (Nissenbaum & Shifman, 2017). Memes act as a powerful tool in achieving the goal of community building, even when the text itself has an unclear meaning. The practice of creation and distribution of memes over the internet is a form of constitutive communication, which is

far more important than the meme’s content. Even the memes that are considered nonsense “always carry effective meaning” (Katz & Shifman, 2017).

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Netnography

Netnography was used for data collection, which is a qualitative research methodology that is interpretative and used to examine the online behavior of brands and consumers. Netnography employs ethnographic techniques to investigate cultural phenomena on the internet. It utilizes information freely accessible to the general public on social media platforms to help understand consumer behavioral patterns. It is considered a marketing research technique that is faster, cheaper, and much simpler than ethnography (Kozinets, 2010).

The focus of this netnographic study is to explore what brands post, how consumers react to it, and how brands respond to it. Therefore, three social media platforms namely Facebook, Instagram, and X, were used to explore which emoji are most frequently used by brands.

Almost 2800 brands’ posts encircling emoji were studied, out of which 2646 posts were conducive. The posts included the general social media posts, as well as the brands’ conversations with the consumers in the form of “comment replies”. After a careful examination, the most used emoji by brands were identified as ❤️, 😊, 🙌, 😄, and 🍷. These emoji were further explored to assess the frequency of these five emoji. Furthermore, the brands using these emoji were also categorized according to their niche. The data collected from netnography is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency of Most Used Emoji by Brands on Facebook, Instagram & X

Brand Categories	Metric	Emoji					Total
		❤️	😊	😄	🙌	🍷	
Food	Frequency	48	82	203	800	12	1145
	Percentage	(4.2%)	(7.2%)	(17.7%)	(70%)	(1.04%)	
Clothing	Frequency	110	20	20	310	9	469
	Percentage	23.45%	4.26%	4.26%	66.09%	1.91%	
Make Up	Frequency	157	19	80	0	0	256
	Percentage	61.32%	7.42%	31.25%			
Online Startups	Frequency	20	0	0	1	205	226
	Percentage	8.84%			1%	90.70%	
Travel	Frequency	509	09	22	0	10	550
	Percentage	92.54%	1.63%	4%		1.81%	
TOTAL		844	130	325	1111	236	2,646

3.2 Content Analysis

The examples of memes and emoji used in this study were extracted from the social media accounts of various brands. A content analysis was then conducted to determine the number of reactions, comments, and shares on these posts to evaluate the success of their efforts to use memes and emoji in their marketing communications. Aside from that, notable comments were also analyzed to determine whether the commenters approved, disapproved, or remained neutral about the content of the posts. An important point to note here is that most social media platforms display comments by ranking them according to their popularity, based on the number of likes each comment receives.

Although memes and emoji are used all over the internet, the most popular social media platforms, i.e., Facebook, Instagram, and X, were selected due to their easy access. Pakistani brands were observed that used emoji and memes in their social media posts. To avoid any ambiguity, platforms such as “Know your Meme” and “Emojipedia” were consulted to clarify the meaning and intent of memes and emoji.

3.2.1 Content Analysis of Memes

HUM TV

Figure 1: HUM TV's Meme Post

On August 2, 2022, HUM TV's official Instagram page posted a meme about the lead actress of one of their top trending drama serials, Bakhtawar. (See Figure 1).

It is clear from the photo that this post is intended as a meme (image macro), designed to grab attention and evoke positive emotions among the audience. The image under study features a girl named Bakhtawar, played by one of the most prominent actresses in the Pakistani drama industry, Yumna Zaidi. She is innocently trying hard to control her tears in this scene, taken from one of Bakhtawar's episodes, and this emotional scene is transformed into a meme. Not to mention, the brand has also employed an emoji in the caption, which is parallel with what the meme is about.

Given the popularity of this brand and drama serial (product), and the fact that it is this brand's first memetic post, it was well-received by the audience. In terms of affinity, as of August 17, 2022, the Instagram post garnered 26,278 likes. Regarding the comments on the post, most were positive, with people appreciating the meme and the actress in the image. Some examples are:

The comments also included people mentioning their friends on the post to remind them of the times that the same happened to them too. Several commenters have also responded without any words, through the use of emoji, such as:

“👍👏 100”

“❤️❤️❤️😍😍”

“😂😂😂😂”

This is an example of a company-generated content. It has the propensity to become viral and also gives the audience a chance to create user-generated content. It can be inferred that using meme marketing is not only effective in reaching a large number of people, but also increases their involvement in what the brand is offering.

Foodpanda

Foodpanda is also one of such brands in Pakistan that utilizes memes and emoji in its online communications. The company generates its memes, more often revolving around the panda, Pau-Pau. (See Figures 2-5). Foodpanda uses memes to attract its customers and build a positive brand image in the minds of consumers.

“She’s such a cutie ❤️” “I cannot stop laughing 😂😂😂”

“I was thinking when watching this scene that this could become a good meme. Expecting more good memes please 😍😊”

“I love this drama”.

Figure 2: Food panda's Meme Post on Instagram

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

These posts are mostly positive as they create feelings of joy and laughter among the audience. Similarly, the relatability of such memes also helps it gain engagement on social media. These posts, altogether, managed to generate almost 1,700 likes and numerous comments. While some of the commenters showed appreciation for memes in the form of words or emoji, the majority of them took the liberty of telling about their disappointing experiences with the brand, such as,

“Yes, please enter in the comedy business, as you can’t provide quality services.”

“Really poor service”

“You guys sent me the wrong order”

This implies that posting memes to attract customers is going to be successful if the brand offers satisfactory products and services to its customers. Otherwise, the memes might backfire. However, it is also worth noting that, regardless of the valence of the comments, the posts are still receiving comments, which indicates that their engagement is increasing.

Astore

Astore is one of Pakistan’s leading brands that specializes in providing affordable and high-quality bags. The brand has become quite famous among social media users and has around 372k followers on its Instagram account. The brand has also started to employ memes in its online communications, with much success (See Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6

Figure 7

These posts hint towards a successful effort of engaging customers with the brand. The memes posted by the brand are humorous, and they have employed instances from different origins to create a memetic post, gathering over 5000 likes in the process. For an online brand with no physical existence, it is really important to keep customers engaged on social media to stay on the map. The comments on the posts also showed that the brand’s customers liked their memes, as mentioned in the comments below:

“Very nice 🍗” “😁” “I love your bags 😁. I have 3”

KFC

KFC also uses memes and emoji in its online brand communications to not only engage its customers but also humanize the brand. The memetic posts on KFC’s Instagram make the brand appear just like a typical social media user (See Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8: KFC’s Meme Post on Instagram

Figure 9

The posts tend to create a friendly connection with the audience. These posts generate feelings of warmth and bonding with the consumers. The posts have managed to gather more than 3000 likes combined. The comments on Figure 8 consist of people making several 🍗 on the post and mentioning their favorite meals from the brand. This helps in generating not only positive word of mouth but also develops a strong bond between the brand and the consumers.

3.2.2 Content Analysis of Emoji

Pakistan Cricket Board

One of the most notable examples of brands using emoji to communicate with their audience is of Pakistan Cricket Board (PCB). The use of emoji in almost all posts of PCB shows their tech-savviness. Their posts are time-saving and fun to read. PCB’s X account was examined in detail, and one of the posts was selected as an example for this study (See Figure 10).

On August 12th, 2022, the Pakistan Cricket Board used their X account to post a picture of the Pakistani cricket team and to inform the world that they are flying to the Netherlands. The caption also included a wish for them to have safe travels in the Dutch language.

This picture depicts perfectly how easily a message can be communicated through the use of emoji. The post garnered a substantial amount of likes, comments, and retweets as of August 17, 2022 (see Table 2).

Figure 10: PCB’s Emoji Post on X

Table 1: PCB Posts’ Engagement on X

Metric	Count
Favorites/Likes	10,000
Retweets	509
Non Quotes	456
Quote Tweets	53
Comments	140

The comments under the post were also analyzed to see if the audience understood what the brand is trying to communicate. The comments were also peppered with emoji, suggesting that the trend of communicating through emoji may persist.

“Champs”

“Best of luck, Team Green. May Allah bless you all with success 😊”

“🇵🇰” “❤️” (green heart) “Best of luck 🏆”

KFC

Another brand that utilizes emoji in its online brand communications is KFC. This brand uploaded a post embedded with emoji in an attempt to engage its audience (See Figure 11).

The post encourages the audience to decipher what the emoji are representing. KFC has effectively utilized emoji to pique its audience's curiosity, which has increased the number of likes and comments on the post.

The engagement with the post signifies that it is well-received by the audience. The post has garnered almost 900 likes and 171 comments. It was observed that KFC's audience enjoyed guessing the emoji, which prompted them to leave comments on the post based on their understanding. It was also noted that KFC "liked" (👍) every comment on the post, which shows that the brand is responding with emoji reactions too.

Figure 11: KFC's Emoji Post on Instagram

Pak Wheels

The brand uses emoji to enhance the meaning of what they are communicating (See Figure 12).

Figure 12: Pak Wheel's Emoji Post on X

The image is sourced from the brand's X account. It shows the brand announcing a good news by employing emoji that portray just that. As mentioned earlier, it is important for a brand to make its online posts distinctive so that the audience stop and take notice. In terms of engagement, the post has gathered almost 223 likes, 15 comments, and nearly 25 retweets.

Table 2: Pak Wheels Posts' Engagement on X

Metric	Count
Favorites/Likes	223
Retweets	25
Non Quotes	10
Quote Tweets	5
Comments	15

3.3 Focus Groups

An exploratory research design was employed to investigate how brands communicating through memes and emoji are perceived by consumers. Purposive sampling was used as a non-probability sampling technique and it was made certain in advance that the sample were social media users with a knowledge about memes and emoji so that their responses were more purposeful to the research (Bell et al., 2022).

3.3.1 Procedure

The sample comprised of 13 female and 7 male participants. The lower age limit was 18 years and the upper age limit was set at 30 years. Four focus groups were conducted with each focus group consisting of 5 participants. All the focus group interviews were recorded and later transcribed. The questions were open and probing, and encouraged participants to respond according to their own opinions.

A traditional inductive qualitative approach was used to analyze the data. Grounded theory was used to analyze respondents' terms, codes and categories. The respondent centric first order codes were grouped to generate researcher centric second order themes, which led to the formation of aggregate dimensions of the emergent data (Bell et al., 2022). (See table 4)

3.3.2 Data Structure

Table 3: Data Structure

Aggregate Dimensions	Second Order Themes	First order Codes
Customer Perception and Reaction	Reaction to the Emoji	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An emoji with the brand message enhances the meaning of it. Emoji can be used when the message is humorous. Complaint handling with the use of emoji/memes will make me angrier. A lot of emoji or memes in brands communication can be regarded as non-serious or fake. High-end brands should not use emoji or memes.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I love trolling people so I share memes that make fun of others.

	Brand- Personality Congruence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some memes resonate with my personality but I don't share them due to societal pressure. • Emoji are convenient. • Replying with emoji or memes is rude.
Brand- Consumer Relationship	Duration of Relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of emoji and memes is okay if I've had a longer relationship with someone. • I wouldn't send you emoji or memes if I'm talking to you for the first time.
	Brand Attitude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I will buy again from this brand because they talked nicely to me. • Entertaining content by brands can form perceptions that lead to brand satisfaction. • Brands who use emoji and memes are modern and up-to-date. • I don't like posts that are detailed. • Use of emoji and memes attract younger audience.
Outcomes	Positive Emotions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seeing my favorite brand using a heart while talking to me made me really happy. • Memes lighten up my mood. • If you don't use emoji, you look rude. • Emoji instantly grab my attention and make me happy. • Some memes are so boring that it look likes the brand is trying too hard to fit in.
	Consumer Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If I like a meme, I tag my friends in the comments. • Memes and emoji make me want to stop scrolling and look at the post. • If a meme is funny, I share it to make others laugh. • Small business use memes to increase their likes and comments,
	Purchase Intentions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I always choose a brand whose social media is entertaining and modern. • Products with high utilitarian component do not require the use emoji and memes.

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Customer Perception and Reaction

4.1.1 Reaction to the Emoji

The use of emoji by brands is preferred by the customers when they are announcing something positive, for instance, launch of a product. Some of the responses correspond to this research, like:

“As long as the brand is posting something useful to me, I would not mind seeing an emoji with it” (Respondent 15).

“Using emoji is fine if it’s accompanied by some text. It makes the tone of the message enjoyable” (Respondent 10).

However, when a brand is displaying greater seriousness or responsibility, individuals could be less open to accepting emoji e.g., the recall of defective products (Glikson et al., 2018). This corresponds with most of the responses, such as:

“When I do not see an emoji in my friend’s message, I automatically assume that she has something profound to say” (Respondent 4).

“I would literally block the page that would reply to my complaint with an emoji” (Respondent 18).

“I suppose it depends on my mood. If the problem is huge, for instance if they have sent me a defected product, their “smile” would make me even angrier. However, if the problem is minor, such as the shipment is late, a “smile” would probably drive my anger away” (Respondent 15).

Furthermore, Emoji-filled texts may be viewed as less trustworthy, according to Willoughby and Liu's (2018) research, which is reflected in the following responses:

“Although I said earlier that people who do not use emoji are fed up with their lives, but I do not think brands should use them. Emoji and memes look great in informal conversations with friends and family. But with brands? No, they are supposed to be professional” (Respondent 10).

“If a brand is replying to me with emoji and memes, or even posting like that on their social media accounts, I would just assume that they are non-serious or probably fake” (Respondent 3).

Similarly, the use of emoji in a brand’s online communications made them appear less competent, evident from the below-mentioned quotes:

“I recall one time when I came across an online business and was inquiring about a product to place an order, and the person kept sending me hearts with every message. It was so creepy, I ended up not ordering from there. I do not know, I just assumed that it was a guy behind the screen, and that made me very uncomfortable” (Respondent 5).

“I do not think that emoji are the right direction for already established brands, especially high end brands. If Maria B. starts posting emoji, who’s going to think that it’s a high-end designer? It will not suit her” (Respondent 12).

“I think online brands (startups) can use emoji” (Respondent 2).

“I think a smile or thumbs-up is okay, but I do not think brands should make hearts” (Respondent 3).

4.1.2 Brand-Personality Congruence

Consumers believe that what they share on social media is a representation of who they are. They are more likely to share entertaining content to make others happy, thereby creating an

impression of them being positive and fun to be around. As is demonstrated by several respondents, like:

“I mostly share memes that tend to insult people in a funny way. Please don’t judge me, I love pranking and trolling my friends all the time” (Respondent 2).

“These days, I have been seeing a lot of memes on Facebook, making fun of “phuppos”, but I can’t post them because I have added my family there. Those memes are sometimes so relatable, but I can’t even mention my siblings in the comments in fear that it might appear on my cousin’s newsfeed” (Respondent 7).

“I really love dark humor, and mean memes. That sometimes, I even feel sad about laughing at them. I don’t share them so that they might welcome negative comments” (Respondent 1).

Consumers prefer to see content from brands with which they can relate. The content they share tends to align with how they perceive themselves or how they aspire to be in the future. This is highlighted in the following quotes:

“I love people who share funny memes. Facebook gives you the option of choosing your favorite friends so you can see all of their posts on your newsfeed instantly. It’s funny I have selected so many of my Facebook friends as my favorites just because they share amazing memes there. I don’t even know them personally, but I like them” (Respondent 5).

“I like a lot of memes but I refrain from sharing them because I fear that they might backfire. Like memes are supposed to make you laugh, but these days, people make a big deal of every little joke. They find every joke to be misogynistic, sexist, discriminatory, or racist” (Respondent 20).

Personality is a big determinant of how memes and emoji are perceived by consumers, as some of the respondents, when asked about how they’d react if they get a meme or emoji as a reply to their complaint, said:

“If I’m writing a feedback and the company replies with a thumbs up, I’d be really annoyed. It just feels like my feedback is of no importance to them” (Respondent 12).

“I think for me, even if the brand replies with an emoji, I’d be happy that at least they replied. You see, brands don’t have time, so it’s convenient for them and I have no problem with it” (Respondent 15).

4.2 Brand-Consumer Relationship

4.2.1 Duration of Relationship

When the brand and consumers are familiar with each other for a long time and have a friend-like relationship, consumers are more receptive towards the use of emoji or memes by them, as is evident from the following responses:

“I suppose I use emoji or humor with my close friends, but if you’re just an acquaintance, I wouldn’t use emoji while talking to you” (Respondent 8).

“I don’t think emoji are a good way to communicate in a professional setting. However, if you have been working with your colleagues for a long time, then I suppose using emoji would be acceptable” (Respondent 9).

4.2.2 Brand Attitude

Research suggests that playfulness in communication has positive outcomes, such as the likelihood of using the same brand’s website again (Ahn et al., 2007), and of generating customer satisfaction (Hsu et al., 2012). Some respondents expressed this by stating:

“I recently ordered a cake from a home-based Instagram page. They sent me a smiling emoji while we were talking. So I also made an emoji with my message. I think I will order again from there just because they talked to me nicely” (Respondent 13).

“I only consider two things while shopping online: the product or service, and the communication by the brand” (Respondent 3).

“I do not know if it falls under memes, but I remember, Ufone used to make really funny and entertaining ads, while the other telecom ads used to be so dull. I got my first phone when I was in 9th grade, and I specifically got a Ufone SIM just because I thought that it was the coolest SIM. I remember my other cousins telling me about Telenor’s better packages, and I would just shrug off, thinking Telenor is for old people” (Respondent 8).

Today’s generation is ad-averse; therefore, the use of visual representation, such as emoji, is important if a brand’s communication efforts are directed towards them (Wu et al., 2017), as is evident from some of the responses:

“I hate reading long posts and captions. I mean, who has the time? If I wanted to read for that long, I would buy a book” (Respondent 1).

“If a brand is using memes and emoji in its posts, I would say it’s up-to-date” (Respondent 5).

“If a brand is targeting young people, using memes and emoji, it can be a good decision. They would be connecting to their target audience, just like we connect with each other. However, I do not think this strategy would work if they are selling products to older people” (Respondent 18).

Memes carry high positive emotional intensity, which connects with the customers, tempting them to share such content that represents them. This results in increased brand engagement, thereby enhancing the image of the brand, as stated by a few respondents:

“I share memes that are relatable and funny” (Respondent 11).

“A brand who is using memes while conversing with its customers, I think would be savvy, and a really chilled-out brand, and being like that myself, I would surely share the content that resonates with me” (Respondent 19).

4.3 Outcomes

4.3.1 Positive Emotions

The use of emoji by brands might promote impressions of warmth, resulting in the creation of personal connection with the brand and generation of emotions (Agnew, 2017; Kelly & Watts, 2015; Luangrath et al., 2017). The following responses prove this claim:

“I love KFC, I’ve been eating it since I was a little child. Once I gave them my feedback on Instagram, and they reacted with ‘heart’ to my message, I felt so good. Although I know that’s just how everybody responds to Instagram messages, and they do not necessarily mean love, but it just made me happy” (Respondent 19).

“I think if someone is making an emoji in the message, and you’re not, then it means you’re being rude. Emoji literally changes the whole tone of what is being said” (Respondent 10).

4.3.2 Customer Engagement

The entertainment value (use of emoji) in a brand’s social media post has a positive influence on customer engagement (Luarn et al., 2015), as is evident from the following response:

“Memes and emoji make you stop and look. Now, even if it is just for a second. You stop to look at what the post is about. You do not do that if it is just some random basic advertisement or a post that’s full of words” (Respondent 6).

Besides this, using internet memes is an effective way to engage customers, and is in fact, considered a better marketing approach than plain advertisements about products (Lee et al., 2019). The following responses were in accordance with this research:

“If I really like a meme, I do not care if it is a brand posting it or some random Facebook page, I would tag my friends, even react “haha”, or whatever, depending on the meme” (Respondent 14).

“I see many brands posting memes on their accounts, especially small businesses. I understand they want likes and comments. Obviously, they want to increase their reach. That’s how Instagram and Facebook’s algorithm works. If a post has a lot of likes and comments, they appear on everyone’s feed” (Respondent 16).

Other responses demonstrate how engaging memes can be, for example:

“I spend a lot of time on social media. It is like you start scrolling and your newsfeed just never ends. Always full of relatable and entertaining stuff. You look at the time suddenly and say, Oh my god! I have spent three hours on my phone” (Respondent 7).

“If I laugh at a meme, I certainly repost or retweet it because I want others to laugh at it too” (Respondent 3).

Pancer et al. (2017) observed that the relationship between the use of emoji in a brand’s communication and customer engagement is positive. Their findings suggest that if an

organization is using emoji in its posts, it is more likely to reach more consumers, as is highlighted by the following response:

“I would most probably like, comment or share a post that’s appealing to the eye. Makes it less boring” (Respondent 6).

4.3.3 Purchase Intentions

Many scholars are of the view that embedding emoji in a brand’s message evoke positive feelings, which result in increased purchase intentions (Coyle & Carmichael, 2019; Das et al., 2019) as quoted by a respondent:

“Whenever I have to go somewhere with my friends, I check that brand’s social media first. If the posts are entertaining and modern, I definitely go to that place” (Respondent 11).

Das et al. (2019) concur with the above notion, however, they believe that this impact can be mediated by positive affect and type of product the consumer is buying, i.e. utilitarian vs. hedonic. This finding is in exact accordance with what one of the respondents narrated:

“I remember, once I was buying an AC on daraz, the reviews were great and everything. While talking to the seller, he seemed kind of non-serious. I mean, he kept making emoji. Now I’m a serious buyer, I’m paying you a big amount. And you see, smiles, or even a heart was fine. But when he asked where I want it delivered, he made a house emoji with the question. Then when he was telling the specifications of the AC, he made the freezing guy emoji to tell me that its cooling is really good. It was really annoying” (Respondent 4).

5. Conclusion

Internet has become a vital part of the modern society. It has facilitated the spread of memes and emoji all over the world, making it a universal internet language. Memes and emoji, despite being a popular internet language, have received limited attention in the marketing perspective. This study was an attempt to investigate how emoji and memes can help in marketing communications. It was argued that adding memes or emoji to a brands’ text-based communication can generate customer engagement.

To examine this, netnography was employed to identify which emoji are most frequently used by brands in their online communications. Moreover, a thorough content analysis was conducted to investigate how local brands utilize memes and emoji in their online communications. After which, focus group interviews were conducted to explore what the general public feels about memes and emoji.

The results of netnography highlighted that the most frequently used emoji by brands are heart (❤️), smile (😊), and a thumbs up (👍). Although a huge number of brands are using emoji in their online communications, the use of emoji is most common in food, makeup, online business, and the clothing industries. An important point highlighted here was that the clothing brands, which use emoji, were those specializing in Western outfits, such as ONE, Outfitters, and Breakout, which are generally worn by the younger generation. This shows that the use of emoji in their communications is done to attract their target audience. Similarly, big designers such as Elan, Maria B., etc. have not employed such techniques in their online messages.

However, a very popular bridal wear designer, Ali Xeeshan was seen to be using hearts and smiles in his conversations. This implies that because the designer's brand personality is funky and colourful, emoji's use by the brand is acceptable for the audience. Similarly, high-end brands in food industry also showed a low trend towards the use of emoji in their online communications. But fast-food brands, such as KFC, McDonalds, Howdy, depict a rising trend of communicating through emoji. Online businesses, such as Foodpanda, Daraz, Export Leftovers, etc. are also employing emoji in its communications.

The content analysis highlighted examples of Pakistani brands using memes and emoji in their social media posts, which depicted that most of the consumer base understood the brands' messages completely. The increased online customer engagement on those posts showed that consumers favored the use of such techniques.

Focus group interviews were conducted to examine the perception of emoji and memes, and their reaction to them. Most of the participants believed that the brand communications can only be successful if appropriate emoji and memes are used. The majority of the respondents did not like the use of hearts in online brand communications, but favored the use of thumbs up and smile as they portray positivity and warmth. However, the group of respondents who considered using heart as a loving gesture from the brand, although slightly less, cannot be ignored.

The positive responses, however, were very powerful as the use of hearts tended to generate stronger connections with the brand and develop positive attitudes. The appropriateness of the memes or emoji varied from person to person. For instance, one respondent viewed ❤️ as an inappropriate emoji for a brand to use; on the other hand, another respondent considered it a nice gesture from the brand.

The findings also suggested that almost all the participants perceived emoji as an informal mode of communication, which makes it an absolute no-go for serious and high-end brands. However, high-end brands can use emoji if it suits their brand personality. This finding resonated with the findings of the netnography. Moreover, the valence of the message also determines how the reader might perceive a message embedded with a meme or emoji. This finding aligns with the content analysis, as most Pakistani brands that use memes and emoji on their social media either belong to the food industry or are already regarded as modern brands.

Similarly, in order for the brand's communications to be successful, it was important that the brand presented itself parallel to the personalities of its target audience.

Furthermore, it was postulated that communicating through memes and emoji can help strengthen consumer-brand relationships, such as brand satisfaction. One of the respondents claimed to have previously chosen a brand solely on the basis of how entertaining and unique its TV advertisements used to be, implying that in today's world, if the social media messages are just as unique and entertaining, they would have the same effect. Not only this, but the duration and the kind of consumer-brand relationship also determined how the use of memes and emoji would be received by the audience.

Brands that communicate through memes and emoji also tend to generate positive outcomes, as indicated by the responses of the participants. The findings suggest that by employing such techniques in online communications, brands can successfully generate positive emotions in the audience, enhance customer engagement, build a distinctive brand image, and increase purchase intentions of consumers.

6. Managerial Implications

This study has several managerial implications. The qualitative work provides managers with ample knowledge on how to appear trendier in today's marketplace. Marketers can portray their brand personality through the use of appropriate emoji, thereby enhancing the meaning of their messages. Not only this, but this research also provides insights for marketers to use emoji when making announcements, launching new products, or sharing good news. Likewise, emoji will not be appreciated by the audience when the message is more serious. Furthermore, marketers can also use emoji in their complaint handling. This will not only help them appear more concerned but also build a positive relation with the user. This research will help marketers devise digital marketing campaigns more strategically, with an increased use of memes and emoji, to benefit their brands and foster stronger relationships with customers. For example, replying to customers' comments or messages with memes and emoji can help generate positive outcomes. This research posits that the brands have to adapt to the changing marketing environment, as memes and emoji continue to grow and spread across digital spaces on a global scale.

7. Future Research

Memes and emoji have started gaining prominence recently, and due to that, exhaustive research on this topic is scarce. Future research can examine the differing interpretations of the various emoji based on gender, age, income, education etc. In this regard, experimental studies can help quantify the comparative attitudes and behaviors towards emoji and memes amongst various socio-demographic groups. Furthermore, researchers can explore the possibility of assessing the front line employees' readiness towards using situation-appropriate emoji, and the subsequent trainings they may require to execute communication as per the brand's personality.

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